

A new unit Weibull distribution(BMUW)

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***Abstract:* A new 2 parameter unit Weibull distribution is defined on the unit interval (0,1). The methodology of deducing its PDF, some of its properties and related functions are discussed. The paper is supplied by many figures illustrating the new distribution and how this can make it illegible to fit a wide range of skewed real data.**

Keywords:

Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, new distribution, unit distribution.

Introduction

Waloddi Weibull(1951) was the first to introduce the Weibull distribution. It is one of the famous distributions used to model life data and reliability. It can describe the increasing failure rate cases as well as the decreasing failure rate cases. The exponential distribution is a special case of it, when the shape parameter is one. Rayleigh distribution is another special case of it, when the shape parameter is 2 . It can also describe and explain the life expectancy of the elements entailed in the fatigue derived failure and can also evaluate the electron tube reliability

and load handling machines. It is used in many fields like medicine, physics, engineering, biology, and quality control. As the distribution does not represent a bathtub or unimodal shapes, this enforces many researchers to generalize and transform this distribution in the recent decades. To mention some of these researchers:, Singla et al. (2012) elucidated beta generalized weibull, Khan et al. (2017) described in details the transmuted weibull, Xie et al. (2002) explored the modified weibull, Lee et al.(2007) clearly explained the beta weibull, Corderio et al. (2010) demonstrated Kumaraswamy weibull, Silva et al. (2010) expounded beta modified weibull, Mudhokar and Srivastav (1993) expatiated the exponentiated weibull, Zhang and Xie (2011) interpreted truncated weibull, Khan and King (2013) explicated transmuted modified weibull, and Marshall and Olkin (1997) handled the extended weibull.

Many distributions were defined on unit interval by many authors. Some of these distributions are:

- 1) Johnson S_B distribution (Johnson, 1949).
- 2) Beta distribution (Eugene et al., 2002).
- 3) Unit Johnson (S_U) distribution (Gündüz & Korkmaz, 2020).
- 4) Topp- Leone distribution (Topp & Leone, 1955).
- 5) Unit Gamma (Consul & Jain, 1971; Grassia, 1977; Mazucheli et al., 2018; Tadikamalla, 1981).
- 6) Unit Logistic distribution (Tadikamalla & Johnson, 1982).

- 7) Kumaraswamy distribution (Kumaraswamy, 1980).
- 8) Unit Burr-III (Modi & Gill, 2020).
- 9) Unit modified Burr-III (Haq et al., 2023).
- 10) Unit Burr-XII (Korkmaz & Chesneau, 2021).
- 11) Unit-Gompertz (Mazucheli, Maringa, et al., 2019).
- 12) Unit-Lindely (Mazucheli, Menezes, et al., 2019).
- 13) Unit-Weibull (Mazucheli et al., 2020).
- 14) Unit Muth distribution (Maya et al., 2024).

Mazucheli et al. (2018) proposed unit Weibull distribution to describe data on the unit interval like the real data he used describing maximum flood level and Petroleum reservoirs data. He proposed a quantile regression model for this unit weibull distribution and found that it sueprexceeded the competing distributions like the beta, Kumaraswamy, Unit Logistic, Simplex, Unit Gamma, Exponentiated Topp-Leone and Extended Arcsine. It has a closed form of the quantile function.

In this paper, another methodology is used to describe a new unit weibull distribution relying on the pdf of the median order statistics of a sample size $n=3$. The author will discuss the new unit 2 parameter distribution Median based unit Weibull (MBUW) and some of its basic properties.

The paper is arranged into 4 sections. In section 1, the author will explain the methodology of obtaining the new distribution. In section 2,

elaboration of its PDF, CDF, Survival function, Hazard function and reversed hazard function will be presented. In section 3, analysis of some real data sets to illustrate to what extent the distribution can fit the data. This is compared with other well-known competitor distributions. In section 4, conclusion and future work will be declared.

Section 1

Methodology:

Derivation of the MBUW Distribution:

Using the pdf of median order statistics of a sample size=3 and parent distribution Weibull, both the scale parameter alpha and shape parameter beta are positive.

$$f_{i:n}(x) = \frac{n!}{(i-1)!(n-i)!} \{F(x)\}^{i-1} \{1-F(x)\}^{n-i} f(x), \quad x > 0$$

$$f_{2:3}(x) = \frac{3!}{(2-1)!(3-1)!} \{F(x)\}^{2-1} \{1-F(x)\}^{3-2} f(x), \quad x > 0$$

$$F(x) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^\beta}, \quad f(x) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^\beta}, \quad x > 0, \quad \alpha \& \beta > 0$$

$$f_{2:3}(x) = 3! \left\{1 - e^{-\frac{x^\beta}{\alpha^\beta}}\right\}^{2-1} \left\{e^{-\frac{x^\beta}{\alpha^\beta}}\right\}^{3-2} \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^\beta}, \quad x > 0$$

$$f_{2:3}(x) = \frac{6}{\alpha^\beta} \beta x^{\beta-1} \left[1 - e^{-\frac{x^\beta}{\alpha^\beta}}\right] \left[e^{-\frac{2x^\beta}{\alpha^\beta}}\right], \quad x > 0, \quad \alpha \& \beta > 0$$

$$f_{2:3}(x) = \frac{6 \beta x^{\beta-1}}{\alpha^\beta} \left[1 - e^{-\frac{x^\beta}{\alpha^\beta}} \right] \left[e^{-\frac{2x^\beta}{\alpha^\beta}} \right], \quad x > 0, \quad \alpha & \beta > 0$$

Using the following transformation:

$$\text{let } y = e^{-x^\beta}$$

$$-\ln(y) = x^\beta$$

$$[-\ln(y)]^{\frac{1}{\beta}} = x$$

$$\frac{dx}{dy} = \frac{1}{\beta} [-\ln(y)]^{\frac{1-\beta}{\beta}} \left(\frac{-1}{y} \right)$$

So the new distribution is the Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) Distribution.

Section 2

Some of the properties of the new distribution (MBUW):

1- The following is the pdf :

$$f(y) = \frac{6}{\alpha^\beta} \left[1 - y^{\frac{1}{\alpha^\beta}} \right] y^{\left(\frac{2}{\alpha^\beta}-1\right)}, \quad 0 < y < 1, \quad \alpha > 0, \quad \beta > 0$$

2- The following is the CDF:

$$F(y) = 3y^{\frac{2}{\alpha^\beta}} - 2y^{\frac{3}{\alpha^\beta}}, \quad 0 < y < 1, \quad \alpha > 0, \quad \beta > 0$$

3- The following is the survival function :

$$S(y) = 1 - F(Y) = 1 - \left(3y^{\frac{2}{\alpha\beta}} - 2y^{\frac{3}{\alpha\beta}} \right) , 0 < y < 1 , \alpha > 0 , \beta > 0$$

4- The following is the hazard function (hf) and reversed hazard function (rhf) respectively:

$$h(y) = \frac{f(y)}{S(y)} = \frac{\frac{6}{\alpha\beta} \left(1 - y^{\frac{1}{\alpha\beta}} \right) y^{\left(\frac{2}{\alpha\beta}-1\right)}}{1 - \left(3y^{\frac{2}{\alpha\beta}} - 2y^{\frac{3}{\alpha\beta}} \right)} , 0 < y < 1 , \alpha > 0 , \beta > 0$$

$$rh(y) = \frac{f(y)}{F(y)} = \frac{\frac{6}{\alpha\beta} \left(1 - y^{\frac{1}{\alpha\beta}} \right) y^{\left(\frac{2}{\alpha\beta}-1\right)}}{3y^{\frac{2}{\alpha\beta}} - 2y^{\frac{3}{\alpha\beta}}} , 0 < y < 1 , \alpha > 0 , \beta > 0$$

The following figures, Fig (1-4), show the PDF for different values of alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5 , 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.1 , 0.6 , 1.1 , 3.5):

Fig. 1: pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1, 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.1) .

Fig. 2: pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1, 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.6)

Fig. 3: pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5 , 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (1.1)

Fig. 4: pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1, 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (3.5)

Fig. 5: pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1, 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (3.5), changing vertical scale.

Fig. 6: cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1, 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.1).

Fig. 7: cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.6).

Fig. 8: cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (1.1).

and beta (1.1).

Fig. 9: cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1, 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (3.5).

Fig. 10: hazard rate of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.1).

Fig. 11: hazard rate of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.6)

Fig. 12: hazard rate of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1, 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (1.1)

Fig. 13: hazard rate of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1, 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (3.5)

Fig. 14: Survival function of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.1)

Fig. 15: Survival function of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.6)

Fig. 16: Survival function of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5 , 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (1.1)

Fig. 17: Survival function of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5 , 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (3.5)

Fig. 18: reversed hazard rate of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.1)

Fig. 19: reversed hazard rate of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (0.6)

Fig. 20: reversed hazard rate of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (1.1)

Fig. 21: reversed hazard rate of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (0.5 , 1 , 1.5, 2 , 2.5 , 3 , 3.5 , 4) and beta (3.5)

Fig.22 : pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (0.1)

Fig.23 : pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (0.6)

Fig.24 : pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (1.1)

Fig.25 : pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (3.5)

Fig.26 : pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (0.1)

Fig.27 : pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (0.6)

Fig.28 : pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (1.1)

Fig.29 : pdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (3.5)

Fig.30 : cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (0.1)

Fig.31 : cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (0.6)

Fig.32 : cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (1.1)

Fig.33 : cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (3.5)

Fig.34 : cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (0.1)

Fig.35 : cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (0.6)

Fig.36 : cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (1.1)

Fig.37 : cdf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (3.5)

Fig.38 : Sf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (0.1)

Fig.39 : Sf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (0.6)

Fig.40 : Sf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (1.1)

Fig.41 : Sf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (3.5)

Fig.42 : Sf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (0.1)

Fig.43 : Sf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (0.6)

Fig.44 : Sf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (1.1)

Fig.45 : Sf of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (3.5)

Fig.46 : hr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (0.1)

Fig.47 : hr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (0.6)

Fig.48 : hr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (1.1)

Fig.49 : hr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (3.5)

Fig.50 : hr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (0.1)

Fig.51 : hr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (0.6)

Fig.52 : hr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (1.1)

Fig.53 : hr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (3.5)

Fig.54 : rhr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (0.1)

Fig.55: rhr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (0.6)

Fig.56 : rhr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (1.1)

Fig.57 : rhr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 0.1 to 1) and beta (3.5)

Fig.58 : rhr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (0.1)

Fig.59 : rhr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (0.6)

Fig.60 : rhr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (1.1)

Fig.61 : rhr of Median Based Unit Weibull (MBUW) distribution, alpha (from 1 to 10) and beta (3.5)

5- Quantile Function:

$$u = F(y) = 3y\frac{2}{\alpha^\beta} - 2y\frac{3}{\alpha^\beta} = -2\left(y\frac{1}{\alpha^\beta}\right)^3 + 3\left(y\frac{1}{\alpha^\beta}\right)^2$$

The inverse of the CDF is used to obtain y , the real root of this 3rd polynomial function is :

$$y = F^{-1}(y) = \left\{ -0.5 \left(\cos \left[\frac{\cos^{-1}(1-2u)}{3} \right] - \sqrt{3} \sin \left[\frac{\cos^{-1}(1-2u)}{3} \right] \right) + 0.5 \right\}^{\alpha^\beta}$$

To generate random variable distributed as MBUR:

- 1- Generate uniform random variable (0,1): $u \sim \text{uniform}(0,1)$.
- 2- Choose alpha and beta levels
- 3- Substitute the above values of u (0,1) and the chosen alpha and beta in the quantile function, to obtain y distributed as $y \sim \text{MBUR}(\alpha, \beta)$

6- rth Raw Moments:

$$E(y^r) = \frac{6}{(2 + r\alpha^\beta)(3 + r\alpha^\beta)}$$

$$E(y^r) = \int_0^1 y^r \frac{6}{\alpha^\beta} \left[1 - y\frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right] y^{\left(\frac{2}{\alpha^\beta}-1\right)} dy$$

$$E(y) = \frac{6}{(2 + \alpha^\beta)(3 + \alpha^\beta)}$$

$$E(y^2) = \frac{6}{(2 + 2\alpha^\beta)(3 + 2\alpha^\beta)}$$

$$E(y^3) = \frac{6}{(2 + 3\alpha^\beta)(3 + 3\alpha^\beta)}$$

$$E(y^4) = \frac{6}{(2 + 4\alpha^\beta)(3 + 4\alpha^\beta)}$$

$$\text{var}(y) = E(y^2) - [E(y)]^2$$

$$\text{var}(y) = \frac{78\alpha^{2\beta} + 60\alpha^{3\beta} + 6\alpha^{4\beta}}{(6 + 10\alpha^\beta + 4\alpha^{2\beta})(6 + 5\alpha^\beta + \alpha^{2\beta})^2}$$

7- Coefficient of Skewness:

$$\begin{aligned} E \frac{(y - \mu)^3}{\sigma^3} &= \frac{E(y^3) - 3\mu E(y^2) + 3\mu^2 E(y) - \mu^3}{\sigma^3} \\ &= \frac{E(y^3) - 3\mu[E(y^2) - \mu E(y)] - \mu^3}{\sigma^3} = \frac{E(y^3) - 3\mu[E(y^2) - \mu\mu] - \mu^3}{\sigma^3} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{coefficient of skewness} = \frac{E(y^3) - 3\mu\sigma^3 - \mu^3}{\sigma^3} = \frac{E(y^3) - \mu(3\sigma^2 + \mu^2)}{\sigma^3}$$

8- Coefficient of Kurtosis:

$$\begin{aligned} E \frac{(y - \mu)^4}{\sigma^4} &= \frac{E(y^4) - 4\mu E(y^3) + 6\mu^2 E(y^2) - 3\mu^4}{\sigma^4} \\ &= \frac{E(y^4) - 4\mu E(y^3) + 6\mu^2[\sigma^2 + \mu^2] - 3\mu^4}{\sigma^4} \\ &= \frac{E(y^4) - 4\mu E(y^3) + 6\mu^2\sigma^2 + 6\mu^4 - 3\mu^4}{\sigma^4} \\ &= \frac{E(y^4) - 4\mu E(y^3) + 6\mu^2\sigma^2 + 3\mu^4}{\sigma^4} = \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{coefficient of Kurtosis} = \frac{E(y^4) - 4\mu E(y^3) + 3\mu^2 [2\sigma^2 + \mu^4]}{\sigma^4}$$

9- Coefficient of Variation :

$$CV = \frac{S}{\mu}$$

The following Figures illustrate the graphs for the above coefficients

Figure 62: the variance and different coefficients with alpha (from 0.1 to 6) & b=0.1.

Figure 63: the variance and different coefficients with alpha (from 0.1 to 6) & $b=0.6$

Figure 64: the variance and different coefficients with alpha (from 0.1 to 6) & $b=1.1$

Figure 64: the variance and different coefficients with alpha (from 0.1 to 6) & b=3.5

10-rth incomplete Moments:

$$E(y^r | y < t) = \int_0^t y^r \frac{6}{\alpha^\beta} \left[1 - y^{\frac{1}{\alpha^\beta}} \right] y^{\left(\frac{2}{\alpha^\beta}-1\right)} dy$$

$$E(y) = \frac{6t^{\frac{2}{\alpha^\beta}+r}}{(2+r\alpha^\beta)} - \frac{6t^{\frac{3}{\alpha^\beta}+r}}{(3+r\alpha^\beta)}$$

Section 3

Some real data analysis:

The same database, OECD, is used. Some variables are analyzed to discover what distributions fit the data better. The data is available at:

<https://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx?DataSetCode=BLI>

First data : (Dwelling Without Basic Facilities)

These observations measure the percentage of homes in the involved countries that lack essential utilities like indoor plumbing, central heating, clean drinking water supplies.

0.008	0.007	0.002	0.094	0.123	0.023	0.005	0.005	0.057	0.004
0.005	0.001	0.004	0.035	0.002	0.006	0.064	0.025	0.112	0.118
0.001	0.259	0.001	0.023	0.009	0.015	0.002	0.003	0.049	0.005
0.001	0.03	0.067	0.138	0.359					

Second data : (Quality of Support Network)

This data set explores how much the person can rely on sources of support like family, friends, or community members in time of need and disparate. It is represented as percentage of persons who had found social support in times of crises.

0.92	0.93	0.88	0.80	0.82	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.94	0.90
0.78	0.98	0.89	0.92	0.91	0.77	0.94	0.95	0.96	0.85

Third data : (Voter Turnout)

This data set evaluates the percentage of capable and qualified persons for casting a vote in election reflecting the democracy in the country.

0.92	0.76	0.88	0.68	0.47	0.53	0.66	0.62	0.85	0.64
0.69	0.75	0.79	0.58	0.70	0.81	0.63	0.67	0.73	0.53
0.77	0.55	0.57	0.90	0.63	0.79	0.82	0.78	0.68	0.49
0.66	0.53	0.72	0.87	0.45	0.86	0.68	0.65		

Fourt data : (Flood Data)

These are 20 observations for the maximum flood level in Susquehanna River at Harrisburg, Penssylvania (Dumonceaux & Antle, 1973) .

0.26	0.27	0.3	0.32	0.32	0.34	0.38	0.38	0.39	0.4
0.41	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.45	0.48	0.49	0.61	0.65	0.74

Fifth data : (Time between Failures of Secondary Reactor Pumps)(Maya et al., 2024, 1999)(Suprawhardana and Prayoto)

0.216	0.015	0.4082	0.0746	0.0358	0.0199	0.0402	0.0101	0.0605
0.0954	0.1359	0.0273	0.0491	0.3465	0.007	0.656	0.106	0.0062
0.4992	0.0614	0.532	0.0347	0.1921				

Sixth data : (to evaluate the factors concerning the unit capacity, data was collected to compare between algorithms like SC 16 and P3)(Maya et al., 2024, 1999)

0.853	0.759	0.866	0.809	0.717	0.544	0.492	0.403	0.344
0.213	0.116	0.116	0.092	0.07	0.059	0.048	0.036	0.029
0.021	0.014	0.011	0.008	0.006				

For the analysis of the above data sets and how the distributions fit them, the following distributions (unit distributions): MBUW and BMUR distributions fitting are conducted and the results are compared with both Beta and Kumaraswamy distributions fitting. The tools for comparison are: negative 2LL, AIC, AIC corrected, BIC, Hannan Quinn Information Criteria (HQIC). K-S test is also conducted with its value reported with the reported result of the H_0 null hypothesis. This hypothesis assumes that the data set follows the tested distribution otherwise reject the null. The P value for the test is also recorded. Histogram of

each data set is shown. Figures of the empirical CDF (ecdf) and the theoretical CDF of the 4 distributions are illustrated. The values of the estimated parameters, their estimated variance and standard errors are reported.

These are the pdfs of the distributions used in the analysis of these 6 data sets, in addition to two distributions that were used in analysis of other data sets provided by the author in a previous preprint paper discussing the new distribution (MBUR).

1- Beta Distribution:

$$f(y; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} y^{\alpha-1} (1 - y)^{\beta-1}, 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0$$

2- Kumaraswamy Distribution:

$$f(y; \alpha, \beta) = \alpha\beta y^{\alpha-1} (1 - y^\alpha)^{\beta-1}, 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0$$

3- Median Based Unit Rayleigh:

$$f(y; \alpha) = \frac{6}{\alpha^2} \left[1 - y^{\frac{1}{\alpha^2}} \right] y^{\left(\frac{2}{\alpha^2}-1\right)}, 0 < y < 1, \alpha > 0$$

4- Topp-Leone Distribution(in previous paper):

$$f(y; \theta) = \theta(2 - 2y) (2y - y^2)^{\theta-1}, 0 < y < 1, \theta > 0$$

5- Unit-Lindley (in previous paper):

$$f(y; \theta) = \frac{\theta^2}{1 + \theta} (1 - y)^3 \exp\left(\frac{-\theta y}{1 - y}\right), 0 < y < 1, \theta > 0$$

Tools of comparison are:

(k) is the number of parameter while (n) is the number of observations.

$AIC = -2MLL + 2k$, where $k =$ number of parameters

$$AIC - corrected = -2MLL + \frac{2k}{n - k - 1}$$

$$HQIC = 2 \log\{\log(n)[k - 2MLL]\}$$

$$BIC = -2MLL + k \log(n)$$

$$KS - test = \text{Sup}_n |F_n - F| , \quad F_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n I_{x_i < x}$$

First data set (Dwelling Without Basic Facilities , n=35):

	Beta		Kumaraswamy		MBUR	MBUW	
theta	$\alpha = 0.4798$		$\alpha = 0.5700$		2.2834	$\alpha = 6.636$	
	$\beta = 9.3996$		$\beta = 6.2579$			$\beta = 0.8726$	
Var	0.0222	0.3127	0.0074	0.1403	0.0011	$3.5 * 10^6$	$-2.5 * 10^5$
	0.3127	7.8562	0.1403	3.7854		$-2.5 * 10^5$	$1.7 * 10^4$
SE	0.025		0.015		0.006	316.227	
	0.474		0.329			22.039	
AIC	161.3608		163.8059		150.585	152.585	
AIC correc	161.7358		164.1809		150.7062	152.9600	
BIC	164.4715		166.9166		152.1403	155.6957	
HQIC	4.3097		4.3132		4.2950	4.2965	
NLL	-78.6804		-79.9029		-74.2925	-74.2925	
K-S Value	0.1818		0.1570		0.1794	0.1794	
H ₀	Fail to reject		Fail to reject		Fail to reject	Fail to Reject	
P- value	0.1744		0.3202		0.1860	0.1860	

Confidence interval for the estimator obtained from fitting MBUR is

(2.27164 , 2.29516)

Fig. 65: Histogram for the first data set (Dwellings without basic facilities).

Fig. 66: shows the eCDF vs. theoretical CDF of the 4 distributions for the 1st data set (both curves of MBUR and MBUW are overlapped).

Second data set (Quality of Support Network, n=20):

	Beta		Kumaraswamy		MBUR	MBUW	
theta	$\alpha = 21.7353$		$\alpha = 16.5447$		0.3591	$\alpha = 0.257$	
	$\beta = 2.4061$		$\beta = 2.772$			$\beta = 1.5073$	
Var	86.4614	9.0379	15.7459	3.2005	0.0008		
	9.0379	1.0646	3.2005	1.0347			
SE	2.079		0.887		0.006	Cannot be estimated	
	0.231		0.227			Cannot be estimated	
AIC	64.5056		64.7274		62.079	64.079	
AIC correc	65.2115		65.4333		62.3012	64.7848	
BIC	66.497		66.7188		63.0747	66.0704	
HQIC	3.9289		3.9299		3.9224	3.927	
NLL	-30.2528		-30.3637		-30.0395	-30.0395	
K-S Value	0.0974		0.0995		0.1309	0.1309	
H ₀	Fail to reject		Fail to reject		Fail to reject	Fail to Reject	
P- value	0.9416		0.9513		0.8399	0.8399	

Confidence interval for the estimator obtained from fitting MBUR is
(0.346542 , 0.371658)

Fig. 67: Histogram for the second data set (Quality of Support Network).

Fig. 68: Fig. 66: shows the eCDF vs. theoretical CDF of the 4 distributions for the 2nd data set (both curves of MBUR and MBUW are overlapped).

Third data set (Voter turnout , n=38):

	Beta		Kumaraswamy		MBUR	MBUW	
theta	$\alpha = 8.6959$		$\alpha = 5.6224$		0.6832	$\alpha = 0.5509$	
	$\beta = 3.8673$		$\beta = 4.5073$			$\beta = 1.2779$	
Var	6.4427	2.3588	0.7462	0.9005	0.0016		
	2.3588	0.9809	0.9005	1.6212			
SE	0.412		0.140		0.006	Cannot be estimated	
	0.161		0.207			Cannot be estimated	
AIC	55.9451		54.8575		46.1377	48.1377	
AIC correc	56.288		55.2003		46.2488	48.4805	
BIC	59.2203		58.1326		47.7753	51.4128	
HQIC	4.063		4.0577		4.0157	4.0216	
NLL	-25.9725		-25.4287		-22.0688	-22.0688	
K-S Value	0.0938		0.1048		0.1364	0.1364	
H ₀	Fail to reject		Fail to reject		Fail to reject	Fail to Reject	
P- value	0.8605		0.7596		0.4401	0.4401	

Confidence interval for the estimator obtained from fitting MBUR is

(0.67144 , 0.69496)

Fig. 69: Histogram for the third data set (voter turnout).

Fig. 70 shows the eCDF vs. theoretical CDF of the 4 distributions for the 3rd data set (both curves of MBUR and MBUW are overlapped).

Fourth data set (Flood data , n=20):

	Beta		Kumaraswamy		MBUR	MBUW	
theta	$\alpha = 6.8318$		$\alpha = 3.3777$		1.0443	$\alpha = 1.0932$	
	$\beta = 9.2376$		$\beta = 12.0057$			$\beta = 0.9719$	
Var	7.22	7.2316	0.3651	2.8825	0.007	$1.66 * 10^4$	$-1.7 * 10^5$
	7.2316	8.0159	2.8825	29.9632		$-1.7 * 10^5$	$1.6 * 10^6$
SE	0.601		0.135		0.019	28.81	
	0.633		1.224			28.81	
AIC	32.3671		29.9465		14.9233	16.9233	
AIC correc	33.073		30.6524		15.1455	17.6292	
BIC	34.3586		31.938		15.9191	18.9148	
HQIC	3.7154		3.6893		3.456	3.4805	
NLL	-14.1836		-12.9733		-6.4617	-6.4617	
K-S Value	0.2063		0.2175		0.3202	0.3202	
H ₀	Fail to reject		Fail to reject		Fail to reject	Fail to Reject	
P- value	0.3174		0.2602		0.0253	0.0253	

Confidence interval for the estimator obtained from fitting MBUR is

(1.004533 , 1.084067)

Fig. 71: Histogram for the fourth data set (voter turnout).

Fig. 72: shows the eCDF vs. theoretical CDF of the 4 distributions for the 4th data set (both curves of MBUR and MBUW are overlapped).

Fifth data set (Time between Failures , n=23):

	Beta		Kumaraswamy		MBUR	MBUW	
theta	$\alpha = 0.6307$		$\alpha = 0.6766$		1.7886	$\alpha = 5.1285$	
	$\beta = 3.2318$		$\beta = 2.936$			$\beta = 0.7113$	
Var	0.071	0.2801	0.0198	0.1033	0.018	$1.02 * 10^7$	$-8.7 * 10^5$
	0.2801	1.647	0.1033	0.9135		$-8.7 * 10^5$	$7.4 * 10^4$
SE	0.056		0.029		0.028	665	
	0.268		0.199			56.7	
AIC	44.0571		44.6592		41.862	43.862	
AIC correc	44.6571		45.2592		42.0525	44.4620	
BIC	46.3281		76.9302		42.9975	46.1330	
HQIC	3.8556		3.8598		3.8472	3.8543	
NLL	-20.0285		-20.3296		-19.9310	-19.9310	
K-S Value	0.1541		0.1393		0.1584	0.1584	
H ₀	Fail to reject		Fail to reject		Fail to reject	Fail to Reject	
P- value	0.5918		0.7123		0.5575	0.5575	

Confidence interval for the estimator obtained from fitting MBUR is

(1.730528 , 1.846672)

Fig. 73: Histogram for the fifth data set (time between failures).

Fig. 74: shows the eCDF vs. theoretical CDF of the 4 distributions for the 5th data set (both curves of MBUR and MBUW are overlapped).

Sixth data set (unit capacity data , n=23):

	Beta		Kumaraswamy		MBUR	MBUW	
theta	$\alpha = 0.4869$		$\alpha = 0.5044$		1.6243	$\alpha = 3.7003$	
	$\beta = 1.1679$		$\beta = 1.1862$			$\beta = 0.7415$	
Var	0.0482	0.0960	0.0166	0.0274	0.0149	$5.2 * 10^6$	$-7.8 * 10^5$
	0.0960	0.2919	0.0274	0.1066		$-7.8 * 10^5$	$1.2 * 10^5$
SE	0.046		0.027		0.025	475	
	0.113		0.068			72.2	
AIC	23.2149		23.3416		17.2158	19.2158	
AIC correc	23.8149		23.9416		17.4062	19.8158	
BIC	25.4859		25.6126		18.3513	21.4867	
HQIC	3.6459		3.6479		3.5572	3.5773	
NLL	-9.6075		-9.6708		-7.6079	-7.6079	
K-S Value	0.1836		0.1790		0.1518	0.1518	
H ₀	Fail to reject		Fail to reject		Fail to reject	Fail to Reject	
P- value	0.3742		0.4051		0.4074	0.4074	

Confidence interval for the estimator obtained from fitting MBUR is
(1.57245 , 1.67615)

Fig. 75: Histogram for the sixth data set (unit capacity factors).

Fig. 76: shows the eCDF vs. theoretical CDF of the 4 distributions for the 6th data set (both curves of MBUR and MBUW are overlapped).

Discussion of the results:

As shown from the analysis of the previous data sets, the median based unit Rayleigh fits the data well as compared to other distributions. It has the lowest values as regards AIC, AIC-corrected, BIC, HQIC and the -2LL. It has also the least SE estimated. The median based unit Weibull is the second distribution that fits the data and it outperforms both the Beta and Kumaraswamy. The histograms of almost all data show skewness. In the figures comparing the empirical CDF and the theoretical CDF, both graphs of MBUR and MBUW are overlapped or they are the same. The confidence interval for the estimator obtained from fitting MBUR is recorded for each data set below the corresponding table. It is also obvious that for second data sets concerning Quality of support network and the third data set concerning voter turnout, the SE could not be estimated by MLE fitting the MBUW distribution. The other data sets also exhibit large variance and near singular variance-covariance matrix which could be solved numerically using a more stable optimization method. This is a problem that can be solved by modified MLE or other methods of estimation like generalized method of moment and its modification. The percentile method and its modification can also be helpful.

Conclusion:

This new distribution overcomes some of the weaknesses of the weibull distribution as regard lack of bathtub and unimodal shapes. It is also defined over the unit interval, so it can be used to fit proportions and ratios. It has a well closed form of quantile function and this makes it compatible for parametric quantile regression conditioning on the median or any other quantile rather than conditioning on the mean which is not a good candidate to describe central tendency in such highly skewed distribution.

Future work:

The author is working on methods of estimation of this new distribution and for its applications in regression analysis. The author also works on methods to better estimate the parameters and to avoid the large variance and the instability of the variance-covariance matrix.

Declarations:**Ethics approval and consent to participate**

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Consent for publication

Not applicable

Availability of data and material

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Competing interests

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Authors' contribution

AI carried the conceptualization by formulating the goals, aims of the research article, formal analysis by applying the statistical, mathematical and computational techniques to synthesize and analyze the hypothetical data, carried the methodology by creating the model, software programming and implementation, supervision, writing, drafting, editing, preparation, and creation of the presenting work.

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